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ENVIRONMENTAL TAXES AND GROWTH-EMISSION TRADE-OFFS: EVIDENCE FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION.

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ABSTRACT:

Reconciling environmental objectives with economic growth remains central to the European Union's pursuit of climate neutrality. This study investigates the heterogeneous effects of environmental taxes on green economic growth across 21 EU countries from 2005 to 2022. Unlike previous studies that overlook cross-country and growth-level heterogeneity, this paper employs quantile-based estimators, the Panel Quantile Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PQARDL) model and the Panel Quantile Regression with Non-Additive Fixed Effects (QRPD) estimator, to capture both short- and long-run dynamics across the growth distribution. The results reveal asymmetric effects: environmental taxation exerts a more pronounced and positive impact on growth in lower-growth (low quantile) economies, where environmental inefficiencies are higher and taxes are less distortionary. Conversely, the marginal benefits diminish in higher-growth (upper quantile) economies, suggesting possible saturation or adjustment costs. These findings underscore the importance of recognising heterogeneity when designing and implementing fiscal instruments for environmental sustainability. Policy implications highlight the need for growth-compatible environmental tax frameworks that are complemented by strategic investments in both human and physical capital. Such an approach can enhance the EU's ability to achieve its long-term climate and economic objectives without compromising competitiveness. By integrating quantile-based evidence into the policy process, this paper advances the empirical understanding of how environmental taxation can reconcile growth and emission objectives within the EU context.

Keywords: Environmental taxation, green economic growth, emissions reduction, panel quantile regression, EU countries, sustainable development.

JEL Codes: C23, Q52, Q56, Q58, O44.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable economic growth remains one of the central policy challenges of the twenty-first century. Climate change, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation continue to jeopardise ecosystems and future development opportunities (Stern, 2007). As the European Union (EU) positions itself as a global leader on climate, environmental taxation has emerged as a key instrument to reconcile economic growth with environmental objectives. Designed to internalise the social costs of pollution, ecological taxes aim to steer production and consumption toward greener alternatives, reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and foster innovation in cleaner technologies (Khan et al., 2023; Hao et al., 2021). However, a fundamental empirical question persists: Do environmental taxes reduce emissions without undermining economic growth across heterogeneous EU economies?

The theoretical foundation for environmental taxation rests on the double dividend hypothesis, which posits that ecological taxes can yield dual benefits, reducing pollution and simultaneously improving economic efficiency if revenues are recycled to lower distortionary taxes or finance productive investments (Bovenberg & de Mooij, 1994; Goulder, 1995). However, empirical findings are far from conclusive. While some studies report that well-designed environmental taxes promote green innovation and long-term growth (OECD, 2022; Morley, 2012), others identify potential short-run trade-offs through higher abatement and production costs (Costa-Campi et al., 2017; Bento, 2013). These divergent results underscore the need for a robust analytical framework that explicitly captures

cross-country heterogeneity and distributional asymmetries in environmental tax effects.

The EU context provides a compelling empirical setting for this inquiry. Through initiatives such as the European Green Deal and the Fit-for-55 package, the EU has introduced a wide array of carbon pricing and environmental tax instruments to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 (European Commission, 2021). However, member states differ significantly in their economic structures, energy dependencies, and institutional capacities. Environmental taxes may be more growth-enhancing in countries with low energy efficiency and greater pollution intensity, yet less effective—or even growth-constraining—in highly developed, energy-efficient economies. Ignoring this distributional heterogeneity risks oversimplifying the growth-emission trade-offs inherent in environmental policy design.

Most existing econometric studies rely on mean-based estimators, which assume uniform effects across the conditional distribution of the dependent variable and mask nonlinear or asymmetric relationships. Such methods overlook the insights offered by quantile-specific estimators (Koenker & Bassett, 1978), particularly when data exhibit skewness, fat tails, or structural asymmetries (Alvarez, 2019). To address these methodological limitations, this study adopts quantile-based panel estimators, specifically, the Panel Quantile Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PQARDL) model and the Panel Quantile Regression with Non-Additive Fixed Effects (QRPD) estimator. The PQARDL model extends quantile regression by capturing both short- and long-run dynamics across the growth distribution (Chudik et al., 2016), while the QRPD approach accounts for unobserved heterogeneity among countries with diverse economic and environmental conditions. Green economic growth is measured using Green GDP, which is defined as the gross domestic product adjusted for environmental degradation and resource depletion. This measure captures the sustainability dimension of development, allowing for a nuanced assessment of whether environmental taxes can "green" growth by decoupling emissions from output expansion.

This study makes several contributions. First, it moves beyond traditional mean-based approaches by applying a distribution-sensitive framework that uncovers how environmental tax effects vary across different points of the green growth distribution. Second, it provides empirical evidence on both the short-term and long-term heterogeneity of these effects, offering richer policy insights for EU member states at different stages of development. Third, by integrating Green GDP per capita as a multidimensional measure of sustainable growth, the study directly engages with the policy debate on whether environmental tax reform can reconcile economic expansion with ecological sustainability.

Generally, this research advances the empirical literature by revealing how distributional dynamics shape the effectiveness of environmental taxes within the EU's broader green transition agenda, thereby contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the growth-emission trade-off in heterogeneous economies.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a review of the related literature, discussing the theoretical underpinnings and empirical findings on environmental taxation, emissions, and economic growth. Section 3 outlines the data and methodology, detailing the construction of the dataset and the rationale for using quantile-based approaches. Section 4 presents and discusses the empirical results, while Section 5 concludes with key policy recommendations for designing effective environmental tax systems in the EU context.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation of environmental taxation is grounded in the externalities approach. Pigou (2017) posits that pollution-generating activities impose social costs not reflected in private decision-making. The Pigouvian tax addresses this by aligning the tax rate with the marginal external damage, thereby internalising the cost and incentivising socially optimal behaviour. This corrective rationale remains central to modern environmental economics.

Building on Pigouvian theory, the double dividend hypothesis (Goulder, 1995) provides a dual justification for environmental taxation. The first dividend arises from pollution reduction, while the second reflects efficiency gains when tax revenues are used to reduce distortionary taxes or finance productive public spending. Although some studies support this dual benefit, others, such as Bovenberg and Goulder (1996), question its generality, arguing that tax interactions can offset efficiency gains. Recent research revisits this debate in the EU context. For example, Vona (2021) finds evidence of a weak double dividend across high-income EU economies, contingent on labour market flexibility and the structure of green fiscal transfers. In contrast, Preuss et al. (2021) suggest that the double dividend can materialise under progressive carbon tax recycling schemes that target vulnerable households and green investment. These evolving insights reinforce the relevance of examining fiscal-environmental trade-offs in a heterogeneous union like the EU.

The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis complements this discussion by linking environmental degradation to income levels. As economies grow, environmental pressure initially intensifies but eventually declines once income surpasses a turning point (Grossman & Krueger, 1995). Environmental taxation can accelerate this transition toward cleaner production by incentivising innovation and behavioural change (Savranlar et al., 2024). However, critiques of the EKC (Dasgupta et al., 2002) and more recent empirical evidence, such as Frodyma et al. (2022) and Bekun et al. (2021), highlight the role of institutional quality, energy mix, and technological adoption in shaping country-specific trajectories, particularly within the EU, where structural asymmetries persist.

Emerging theoretical literature emphasises the distributional heterogeneity of environmental tax impacts. Chu et al. (2024) and Vona (2021) argue that the growth and welfare effects of such taxes depend critically on a country's industrial composition, level of green innovation, and governance structure. These findings underpin our study's quantile-based approach, which explicitly models asymmetries across different growth quantiles of Green GDP. This measure adjusts gross domestic product for environmental degradation and resource depletion, thereby capturing the sustainability dimension of economic performance.

In synthesising these perspectives, this paper draws on four interrelated theoretical clusters: (i) Pigouvian externality theory, (ii) the double dividend hypothesis, (iii) the Environmental Kuznets Curve, and (iv) contemporary theories on heterogeneity and distributional asymmetry. Together, these frameworks illuminate the complex trade-offs between environmental taxation, economic growth, and emissions within a union of structurally diverse economies. They also justify the need for empirical methods, such as the PQARDL model and the Panel Quantile Regression with QRPD, that capture heterogeneous dynamics across the conditional distribution of green growth outcomes.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Empirical evidence on environmental taxation reveals mixed and often context-dependent results. Early studies (Metcalf & Stock, 2020; Andersen, 2019) report that carbon taxes in European economies have effectively reduced GHG emissions without significant adverse effects on long-term growth. However, the strength and direction of these effects vary across countries and depend on tax design, industrial structure, and energy dependency. Klenert et al. (2018) demonstrate that uniform carbon taxes have regressive impacts unless paired with redistributive fiscal mechanisms. In contrast, Olasehinde-Williams et al. (2025) highlight that emerging EU economies often experience more substantial short-term output losses due to higher energy intensities and weaker innovation ecosystems.

The double dividend literature remains divided. While Bosquet (2000) and Wu et al. (2020) provide evidence supporting fiscal and environmental gains from revenue recycling, Mazzucato and Perez (2023) find that the second dividend is contingent on innovation-oriented recycling strategies, particularly when revenues finance low-carbon R&D or energy transition subsidies. Conversely, Ville (2023) argue that in advanced EU economies, carbon tax-induced welfare gains are often offset by competitiveness pressures in energy-intensive industries. This ongoing debate highlights the need for a nuanced approach that considers distributional differences in fiscal capacity and industrial resilience. The EKC has also been empirically tested in the EU with varying results. Apergis and Ozturk (2015) found evidence supporting the EKC, whereas Stern (2004) challenged its universality. Recent EU-focused analyses such as Wolde-Rufael and Mulat-Weldemeskel (2023) and Demiral and Akça (2022) confirm that environmental taxation can flatten the EKC by reducing pollution intensity but caution that policy effectiveness depends on institutional quality, energy diversification, and the timing of implementation. These findings suggest that a one-size-fits-all carbon taxation model may not yield uniform growth and environmental outcomes across EU member states.

Furthermore, recent methodological progress in quantile regression for panel data provides new tools to address these complexities. Opoku and Aluko (2021) and Audi et al. (2025) advance quantile autoregressive frameworks that account for unobserved heterogeneity, fat-tailed distributions, and temporal dependencies, making them particularly suitable for evaluating policies with asymmetric impacts, such as environmental taxes. Hawitibo and Tenaw (2022) further demonstrate that traditional mean-based estimators obscure critical distributional effects, especially when country-level growth responses are nonlinear and context-sensitive. These methodological advances support our use of PQARDL and QRPD estimators, which uncover both short-run and long-run heterogeneity across the distribution of green growth in EU economies.

Finally, recent EU evidence supports the existence of differentiated effects of environmental taxation. Sun et al. (2025) argued that ecological tax incentives significantly enhance green total factor productivity when directed toward clean energy R&D, while Nguyen and Duong (2025) document asymmetric growth impacts, stronger in emerging EU economies and weaker, sometimes negative, in highly industrialised ones. Köppl and Schratzenstaller (2023) similarly note that the distributional outcomes of carbon taxes hinge on institutional efficiency and public investment in green infrastructure.

2.3 Research Gap

Collectively, these studies reveal that the effectiveness of environmental taxation in achieving growth-

emission balance depends not only on policy design but also on the heterogeneity of member states. The present study advances this debate by applying *quantile-based panel estimators* that move beyond average effects to reveal the full conditional distribution of environmental tax impacts across EU economies. By integrating recent econometric innovations and focusing on *Green GDP* as a comprehensive indicator of sustainable growth, this work makes both theoretical and empirical contributions to the ongoing discussion on how fiscal instruments can reconcile economic and environmental objectives in a diverse union.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data

This study examines the role of environmental taxation in promoting **green economic growth**, focusing on its impact, together with selected macroeconomic and environmental control variables, on the green GDP of a panel of EU-27 countries. A structured panel dataset is compiled using the variables defined in Equation (1), covering the most extended possible period for which reliable data is available. The analytical sample comprises 21 EU member states with consistent and complete data from 2005 to 2022, representing the longest reliable time span with harmonised Eurostat and World Bank indicators for environmental taxes and GDP. Six countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Malta, Latvia, and Romania) are excluded due to substantial data gaps, particularly in environmental accounting variables. This exclusion may limit the generalizability of the findings to newer or smaller EU economies with less mature environmental reporting frameworks; however, the retained sample still accounts for over 90% of the EU's total GDP and emissions. The period from 2005 to 2022 is marked by major institutional and policy milestones, including the implementation of the EU Emissions Trading System (Phase II in 2005), the post-2010 fiscal consolidation phase, and the post-2020 green recovery and climate neutrality commitments following the COVID-19 shock. These structural breaks capture critical phases in the evolution of Europe's environmental tax regime. The final set of countries includes Belgium, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Estonia, Ireland, Greece, Spain, France, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Hungary, the Netherlands, Austria, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Slovakia, Finland, and Sweden.

$$GGDP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ENVT_{it} + \beta_2 HINF_{it} + \beta_3 INTR_{it} + \beta_4 PCAP_{it} + \beta_5 HCAP_{it} + \beta_6 GHG_{it} + \beta_7 EXR_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where: GGDP represents Green GDP, ENVT represents environmental tax, HINF represents headline inflation, INTR represents the interest rate, PCAP represents physical capital, HCAP represents human capital, GHG represents greenhouse gas emissions, and EXR represents the exchange rate. For empirical analysis, the variables GGDP, ENVT, PCAP, HCAP, and EXR were employed in their logarithmic forms.

This study employs *Green GDP (GGDP)* as an environmentally adjusted indicator of economic performance, designed to account for the depletion of natural resources and environmental externalities that conventional GDP omits. Following Stjepanovic et al. (2022), GGDP is computed as gross value added plus taxes (minus subsidies) adjusted for three environmental cost components: (i) the monetary cost of CO₂ emissions, estimated as total emissions multiplied by the corresponding EU carbon price; (ii) the opportunity cost of waste, measured as the forgone electricity generation from one ton of waste; and (iii) natural resource depletion, proxied by its share in gross national income.

This formulation captures inter-country heterogeneity arising from differences in carbon intensity, industrial structure, energy mix, and the strictness of environmental policies. Over time, variation in GGDP reflects structural transitions within national economies, such as shifts toward cleaner production, adoption of renewable technologies, and changing carbon pricing trajectories, making it a dynamic and policy-sensitive measure of green growth.

Environmental tax data comprises four categories: energy taxes (petrol, diesel, fuel oils, natural gas, coal, electricity, and carbon instruments), pollution taxes (air, water, noise, and solid waste), resource taxes (forests, water, flora, fauna), and transport taxes (vehicle ownership/use). Data are sourced from the ONS and Eurostat. Equation (1) also controls for human capital, physical capital, inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, and greenhouse gas emissions to assess green growth dynamics.

The inclusion of control variables in this study is based on both theoretical and empirical reasoning to ensure a comprehensive assessment of the growth–emission trade-off in the European Union. As detailed in Table 1, all series were obtained from reputable secondary sources, including the World Bank's *World Development Indicators (WDI)*, ensuring consistency and comparability across countries.

Headline inflation and interest rates are included to capture macroeconomic stability and monetary conditions that influence both investment decisions and production efficiency, thereby affecting the responsiveness of growth to environmental taxation. Exchange rate variations are considered because they shape external competitiveness and the relative cost of green imports and exports, which can moderate the link between taxation and green growth. Physical capital, proxied by gross fixed capital formation, reflects productive investment capacity and technological upgrading, both of which are critical for transitioning toward low-carbon production. Human capital, measured through educational attainment or the human capital index, is a key determinant of innovation and the effective adoption of cleaner technologies, influencing how economies absorb and respond to environmental policies. Finally, GHG emissions serve as an environmental performance indicator, directly linking the effectiveness of ecological taxation to the outcomes of emissions. Collectively, these controls align with existing literature and ensure that the estimated effects of environmental taxes on green GDP are not confounded by omitted macroeconomic or structural influences.

Table 1. Definition and Sources of Variables

Variable	Definition	Unit of measurement	Source
GGDP	Green GDP	USD	https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/24vbg29y48/1
ENVT	Environmental tax	% of GDP	https://climatedata.imf.org/datasets/3fb1ed30d3394574b3145246846023b1_0/about
HINF	Headline inflation	Index	https://www.worldbank.org/en/research/brief/inflation-database
INTR	Interest rate	%	https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators#
EXR	Exchange rate	National currency units per USD	https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators#
PCAP	Physical capital	USD	https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators#
HCAP	Human capital	% of the working-age population with basic education	https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators#
GHG	Greenhouse gas emissions	Mt CO ₂ e	https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators#

3.2 METHODS OF ANALYSIS

3.2.1 Panel Quantile Regression Analysis

Environmental and economic datasets often exhibit heavy tails, skewness, and extreme values, limiting the reliability of mean-based regressions that assume homogeneous effects across the dependent variable's distribution (Chu et al., 2023). In environmental policy, such assumptions rarely hold; for example, ecological taxes may influence economies differently depending on their level of green growth. Failing to account for these differences risks providing recommendations that are incomplete or misleading. To address this, the study employs panel quantile regression techniques, specifically PQARDL and QRPD, which capture distributional asymmetries and heterogeneous effects, thereby providing a more nuanced understanding of how environmental taxation influences green growth trajectories across varying performance levels.

3.2.2 Panel QARDL Analysis

The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) framework of Pesaran et al. (2001) is widely applied due to its versatility in modelling short-run adjustments and long-run equilibrium relationships, even with variables of mixed integration orders, provided none exceed I(1) (Jordan & Philips, 2018; Olasehinde-Williams & Köksal, 2025). To extend its relevance in contexts of distributional heterogeneity, the quantile ARDL (QARDL) was developed. Quantile regression techniques move beyond conditional means, enabling analysis across the entire distribution of the dependent variable, which is critical when data exhibit non-normality or nonlinearities.

QARDL allows parameter estimates to vary across quantiles, capturing locational asymmetries and quantile-dependent cointegration patterns often missed by mean-based models. Unlike nonlinear

threshold approaches, QARDL identifies nonlinearity in an entirely data-driven manner (Shahbaz et al., 2018; Olasehinde-Williams et al., 2024). This study employs the panel QARDL (PQARDL), as developed by Cho et al. (2015), implemented by Godil et al. (2020), and adapted by Arshed et al. (2022) to incorporate fixed effects, thereby addressing unobserved heterogeneity.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LGGDP}_{it} = & \alpha_i(\tau) + \sum_{j=1}^p \phi_{1j}(\tau)\text{LGGDP}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_1} \beta_{1j}(\tau)\text{LENVT}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_2} \beta_{2j}(\tau)\text{HINF}_{it-j} + \\ & \sum_{j=0}^{q_3} \beta_{3j}(\tau)\text{INTR}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_4} \beta_{4j}(\tau)\text{LPCAP}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_5} \beta_{5j}(\tau)\text{LHCAP}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_6} \beta_{6j}(\tau)\text{GHG}_{it-j} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^{q_7} \beta_{7j}(\tau)\text{LEXR}_{it-j} + \varepsilon_{it}(\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where: $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ indexes cross-sectional units (countries), $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ indexes time, $\tau \in (0, 1)$ denotes the quantile, p and q_k represent lag orders for the dependent and independent variables, respectively.

Re-parameterising the PQARDL into its **Error Correction Model (ECM)** form for quantile τ :

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\text{LGGDP}_{it} = & \varphi_i(\tau)[\text{LGGDP}_{it-1} - \theta_1(\tau)\text{LENVT}_{it-1} - \theta_2(\tau)\text{HINF}_{it-1} - \theta_3(\tau)\text{INTR}_{it-1} - \\ & \theta_4(\tau)\text{LPCAP}_{it-1} - \theta_5(\tau)\text{LHCAP}_{it-1} - \theta_6(\tau)\text{GHG}_{it-1} - \theta_7(\tau)\text{LEXR}_{it-1}] + \\ & \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \lambda_{1j}(\tau)\Delta\text{LGGDP}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_1-1} \delta_{1j}(\tau)\Delta\text{LENVT}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_2-1} \delta_{2j}(\tau)\Delta\text{HINF}_{it-j} + \\ & \sum_{j=0}^{q_3-1} \delta_{3j}(\tau)\Delta\text{INTR}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_4-1} \delta_{4j}(\tau)\Delta\text{LPCAP}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_5-1} \delta_{5j}(\tau)\Delta\text{LHCAP}_{it-j} + \\ & \sum_{j=0}^{q_6-1} \delta_{6j}(\tau)\Delta\text{GHG}_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_7-1} \delta_{7j}(\tau)\Delta\text{LEXR}_{it-j} + \mu_{it}(\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here: $\varphi_i(\tau)$ is the **speed of adjustment** to the long-run equilibrium, $\theta_k(\tau)$ are the long-run coefficients, $\delta_{kj}(\tau)$ are the short-run dynamic coefficients, $\mu_{it}(\tau)$ is the quantile-specific error term.

For this study, the PQARDL model is estimated for multiple quantiles ($\tau = 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.25, 0.30, 0.35, 0.40, 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.60, 0.65, 0.70, 0.85, 0.90, 0.95$) to capture the distributional heterogeneity of environmental tax effects on green GDP. The long-run coefficients are derived from the lagged level terms, while short-run effects are captured through the differenced regressors.

The choice of lag orders (p, q_1, \dots, q_7) is based on information criteria (AIC). Inference is conducted using bootstrap standard errors to ensure robustness to heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation. Optimal lag lengths are determined endogenously for each quantile and variable, allowing for heterogeneous dynamic adjustments across countries and growth distributions—consistent with the quantile-based framework's emphasis on capturing nonlinear and asymmetric responses.

3.2.3 Panel Method of Moments Quantile Regression with Fixed Effects

While the PQARDL model captures short- and long-run dynamics between environmental tax and green GDP, robustness checks are necessary. Thus, the study employs Powell's (2022) panel quantile regression with non-additive fixed effects, which avoids the interpretational issues of additive fixed effects (Canay, 2011; Powell, 2022). This framework enhances interpretability by preserving the non-separability of errors, thereby maintaining the model's integrity and accuracy. It offers key advantages: consistent estimates with short panels, robustness to non-normal errors and endogeneity, and resilience to cross-sectional dependence and nonstationarity. Estimation relies on simulation-based Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), implemented with 1,000 draws and a 100-draw burn-in to ensure convergence (Byaro et al., 2023).

Formally, the panel quantile regression model with non-additive fixed effects can be expressed as:

$$\text{GGDP}_{it} = D'_{i,t}\beta(U_{it}^*) U_{it}^* \sim (1,0) \quad (4)$$

Where: $D'_{i,t}$ represents the vector of all regressors included in eq. (1). $U_{i,t}^*$ refers to the error term. For a particular country i for a specific year, t in a specific quantile τ , the panel quantile regression model relies on the condition that.

$$P(\text{GGDP}_{it} \leq D'_{it}\beta(\tau) | D'_{it}) = \tau \tag{5}$$

For any regressors, the probability that green growth falls below the quantile function equals τ . The model, estimated across $\tau=0.10-0.90$ using GMM, yields $\beta(\tau)$ and captures heterogeneous tax effects. Comparing QRPD with PQARDL tests robustness, ensuring consistent results despite differing assumptions on dynamics, lags, and fixed effects.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

4.1 Correlation Analysis

A quantile-specific correlation analysis is first conducted to explore the dependence between environmental taxes and green GDP across the distribution. Serving as a diagnostic step, this avoids restricting inference to mean effects and detects heterogeneity. The study employs the quantile correlation sure independence screening (QC-SIS) method of Ma and Zhang (2016), which is robust to outliers and captures nonlinear associations, thereby pre-identifying quantiles where the tax–growth relationship is substantial. Results (Table 2) reveal heterogeneity: lower quantiles (0.1–0.5) show strong positive effects, most pronounced at 0.2 (0.228), suggesting taxes significantly foster green growth in less green-intensive economies. Mid quantiles (0.6–0.7) yield insignificant effects, likely reflecting the dominance of structural and technological factors in shaping policy. Upper quantiles (0.8–0.9) regain significance, with 0.9 (0.153) indicating taxes reinforce sustainability by promoting innovation and efficiency. Overall, QC-SIS confirms the non-uniform impact of ecological taxes and validates subsequent PQARDL and MM-QR estimations for robust distribution-sensitive analysis.

Table 2. QC-SIS Result

Quantile	Coefficient	P-value	Correlation detected
0.1	0.111 ^c	0.053	Yes
0.2	0.228 ^a	0.000	Yes
0.3	0.129 ^b	0.016	Yes
0.4	0.211 ^a	0.000	Yes
0.5	0.109 ^b	0.046	Yes
0.6	0.006	0.914	No
0.7	0.051	0.356	No
0.8	0.115 ^b	0.032	Yes
0.9	0.153 ^a	0.003	Yes

Note: ^a, ^b and ^c denote statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10 % respectively.

4.2 Unit Root Tests

Before estimating the models, the integration properties of the data are examined to prevent spurious regressions and ensure compatibility with the chosen frameworks. While PQARDL accommodates $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ variables but not $I(2)$, the QRPD approach is more robust to nonstationarity, making unit root testing essential for model specification and inference credibility. A combination of first- and second-generation panel unit root tests, Im, Pesaran and Shin (2003), ADF-Fisher (Maddala & Wu,

1999), and cross-sectionally augmented IPS (Pesaran, 2007), is applied. Results (Table 3) show mixed integration orders, with all nonstationary variables achieving stationarity after first differencing.

Table 3. Unit root test results

Test statistics	GGDP	ENVT	HINF	INTR	PCAP	HCAP	EXR	GHG
Level								
IPS	0.334	1.557	-4.619 ^a	-2.358 ^a	-0.120	-0.874	2.279	-0.377
ADF-Fisher	21.471	31.386	86.800 ^a	57.715 ^c	30.330	51.419	15.841	40.953
CIPS	-1.836	-2.434	-2.459 ^a	-4.725 ^a	-1.764	-1.627	-1.376	-1.954
First Difference								
IPS	-6.481 ^a	-3.706 ^a			-2.566 ^a	-4.947 ^a	-5.419 ^a	-2.552 ^a
ADF-Fisher	116.393 ^a	81.943 ^a			66.354 ^a	104.678 ^a	96.192 ^a	70.216 ^b
CIPS	-3.274 ^a	-3.032 ^a			-3.398 ^a	-3.664 ^a	-4.631 ^a	-3.788 ^a

Note: ^a, ^b and ^c denote statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10 % respectively.

4.3 PQARDL Estimation Results

The PQARDL long-run estimates are reported in Table 4, with the graphical representation of the outcomes presented in Fig. 1.² Although the effect of environmental taxation is positive and predominantly statistically significant, the long-run estimates reveal an apparent distributional asymmetry in the relationship between ecological taxation and green growth.

The effects are most significant at the lower tail ($\tau=0.05-0.50$), indicating that tax-based incentives deliver the most critical marginal gains where green growth is weakest. A plausible mechanism is that lagging economies have abundant “low-hanging fruit” (energy-efficiency upgrades, pollution-abatement retrofits, and adoption of proven clean technologies) that become immediately profitable once environmental taxes tilt relative prices. Moving toward the middle of the distribution ($\tau = 0.60-0.70$), coefficients diminish and lose statistical significance, suggesting a plateau. Once basic efficiency improvements are exhausted and institutional frictions (e.g., procurement rigidities, financing constraints) become binding, additional tax pressure translates less readily into measured green growth. At the upper tail ($\tau \geq 0.75$), the positive impact re-emerges, consistent with high-performing economies using tax signals to sustain innovation (e.g., scaling renewables, storage, and green R&D) and to secure a competitive advantage in clean value chains.

These patterns are consistent with the CQ-SIS results reported in Table 2. The CQ-SIS indicated stronger positive dependence between environmental taxes and green growth at the extremes of the distribution and a muted association around the median. PQARDL, by modelling dynamics and controlling covariates, corroborates that descriptive pattern with conditional, distribution-specific elasticities. In particular, the strong coefficients at the lower half of the PQARDL quantiles align with the dense clusters of positive correlation observed in the lower quantiles of CQ-SIS. At the same time, the re-intensification at $\tau \geq 0.75$ mirrors the upper-quantile correlation clusters. The fade-out near the centre of the distribution is also shared across methods, suggesting that the mid-performing group benefits neither from the easy gains of late adopters nor from the innovation and scale economies of leaders. In short, PQARDL confirms that the bivariate dependence revealed by CQ-SIS is not spurious:

² Short-run estimates are only presented graphically in Fig. 1, as they are predominantly insignificant.

it persists after accounting for persistence, controls, and fixed effects, and it operates through quantile-specific channels.

The distributional shape we uncover is consistent with several strands of the extant literature. First, it aligns with the Porter hypothesis and subsequent empirical work, which show that well-designed environmental pricing can stimulate efficiency and innovation (Porter, 1996; Xepapadeas & de Zeeuw, 1999; Ahmed et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Olasehinde-Williams & Folorunsho, 2025). Second, our lower-tail results align with evidence that carbon and energy taxes can yield substantial improvements when abatement costs are initially low and technologies are readily available (see, for instance, Andersson, 2019). Third, the revival of positive effects at high quantiles aligns with research on directed technical change, whereby stronger price signals tilt innovation toward cleaner technologies once an economy is already near the frontier (Aghion et al., 2016). Together, these studies help explain why the impact of environmental taxes is most significant for late adopters (easy efficiency gains) and leaders (innovation margins) but attenuated for middle performers that face organisational and financial constraints without yet enjoying frontier-level innovation ecosystems.

Figure 1. Plots of the PQARDL short- and long-run coefficient estimates across quantiles

PQARDL long-run estimates (Table 4; Fig. 1) reveal heterogeneous effects of controls on green GDP. Inflation is negative and significant across all quantiles, indicating that price instability hampers green growth. Exchange rates also consistently show adverse effects, intensifying at upper quantiles, suggesting that currency depreciation raises the costs of green technologies. GHG emissions have a substantial negative impact, especially at lower quantiles, reflecting the trade-off between economic growth and environmental sustainability. Human capital becomes positive and significant only beyond

$\tau = 0.65$, aligning with the concept of skill-biased technological change. Interest rates are mostly insignificant. Physical capital strongly promotes green growth, particularly at lower quantiles, highlighting its centrality in early transitions.

4.4 QRPD Estimation Results

The QRPD results presented in Table 5 serve as a robustness check to earlier PQARDL results, allowing us to verify whether the observed patterns are consistent across different econometric specifications.

Across almost all quantiles up to $\tau = 0.80$, environmental taxes exert a positive and statistically significant influence on green GDP. However, the magnitude of this effect diminishes as we move from the lower to the upper quantiles. Specifically, the most potent effects are found in the lower tail of the distribution, suggesting that environmental taxes yield their most considerable marginal benefits in economies with weaker green growth performance. This aligns with the notion that such economies possess greater untapped efficiency gains, scope for adoption of cleaner technology, and opportunities for structural transformation when appropriately incentivised. The gradual decline in coefficients toward the median and upper quantiles indicates that as economies achieve higher levels of green growth, the marginal returns to environmental taxation diminish, possibly due to prior saturation in technological and regulatory gains.

Nevertheless, the persistence of statistical significance up to $\tau = 0.80$ suggests that environmental fiscal measures remain relevant even in relatively high-performing economies. The only exception is at $\tau = 0.90$, where the coefficient turns statistically insignificant. These results reinforce the PQARDL and QC-SIS findings, which also indicated a positive but heterogeneous relationship between environmental taxation and green growth, validating the robustness of the earlier conclusions.

In addition, the exchange rate exhibits a consistently negative and highly significant effect across all quantiles, with the magnitude of this adverse impact increasing from -0.022 at $\tau = 0.10$ to -0.063 at $\tau = 0.90$. This suggests that currency depreciation is generally detrimental to green growth, and its harmful effects are more pronounced in higher-performing economies. The PQARDL results similarly documented a persistent negative exchange rate–green growth link, indicating that this adverse relationship is not sensitive to the modelling approach. GHG emissions display a uniformly negative effect on green GDP, with the magnitude gradually declining across quantiles from -0.019 at $\tau = 0.10$ to -0.012 at $\tau = 0.90$. This pattern confirms the inverse association between environmental degradation and green economic performance, in line with the PQARDL estimates. Headline inflation exerts a statistically significant and negative influence on green GDP across all quantiles, with its magnitude intensifying in higher quantiles (from -0.025 at $\tau = 0.10$ to -0.038 at $\tau = 0.90$). This finding, in line with the PQARDL outcomes, indicates that inflationary pressures may erode the economic space for green investments and heighten uncertainty, thereby affecting both low- and high-performing economies. The more potent effects at higher quantiles may reflect the higher costs of sustaining green infrastructure and innovation in already advanced green economies under inflationary conditions. As for human capital, while its effect is insignificant primarily at lower quantiles, it becomes significant at $\tau = 0.70$ and beyond. This confirms the earlier finding from the PQARDL estimates that higher levels of human capital become critical for advancing green growth only after a certain developmental threshold is reached, consistent with theories of skill-biased technological change in the environmental

sector. Physical capital consistently exerts a large, positive, and highly significant effect on green GDP across all quantiles, with coefficients declining slightly from 1.018 at $\tau = 0.10$ to 0.916 at $\tau = 0.90$. This finding underscores the crucial role of investment in physical infrastructure, including renewable energy facilities, sustainable transportation systems, and energy-efficient industrial equipment, in fostering green growth. The PQARDL results similarly highlighted the strong contribution of physical capital, confirming that this driver is robust to different estimation approaches.

From a policy perspective, these results reinforce the robustness of earlier PQARDL findings, while adding a richer distributional perspective. The evidence supports the Porter Hypothesis in that well-designed environmental taxes can stimulate efficiency improvements and innovation, particularly in lower-performing economies. At the same time, the consistent negative impacts of exchange rate depreciation, inflation, and GHG emissions highlight the need for macroeconomic stability and environmental protection to sustain green growth. The quantile-specific differences in the roles of human and physical capital suggest that policy priorities should be tailored to an economy's position along the green growth spectrum, emphasising foundational infrastructure in low-performing economies and advanced skill development in higher-performing ones.

4.5 Additional Robustness Checks

The robustness of the quantile-based findings is assessed using random-effects (RE) and fixed-effects (FE) regressions with Driscoll–Kraay standard errors, which correct for heteroskedasticity, serial correlation, and cross-sectional dependence (Tables 6–7; Fig. 2). These estimates broadly align with PQARDL and QRPD results, confirming the stability of the key relationships across methods.

Environmental tax remains a positive and highly significant determinant of Green GDP. In quantile models, the effect is most potent at lower quantiles and diminishes at higher ones, reflecting a tapering role in greener economies. The Driscoll–Kraay regressions corroborate this: RE yields 0.317, consistent with lower to mid quantiles, while FE yields 0.224, which is still significant. This convergence underscores the robustness of environmental taxation's growth-enhancing role.

Exchange rate depreciation consistently harms Green GDP. The RE (–0.047) and FE (–0.040) estimates align with the mid-to-upper quantiles, confirming the PQARDL findings of more substantial long-run effects. Similarly, greenhouse gas emissions remain negative across all models, with RE (–0.030) and FE (–0.016) being significant, which reinforces the incompatibility of environmental degradation with green growth. The strong positive effect of physical capital is also preserved: FE (0.976) closely mirrors the quantile-based coefficients, which are near unity, underscoring its centrality in driving sustainable development.

Inflation and human capital show some divergence. Inflation is negative and significant in QRPD and PQARDL but mixed in Driscoll–Kraay: RE is insignificant, whereas FE (–0.030) indicates adverse within-country effects, suggesting the relationship is more pronounced in domestic contexts. Human capital proves quantile-dependent in QRPD, with a positive relationship at higher levels of green growth. PQARDL offers mixed evidence, while Driscoll–Kraay RE reports a significant positive effect (0.105), reflecting between-country variation, but FE shows no significance.

Overall, Driscoll–Kraay estimations validate the main findings: environmental taxation, exchange rates, emissions, and physical capital exert robust effects regardless of specification. Quantile approaches enrich understanding of heterogeneity across the distribution, while Driscoll–Kraay

confirms these relationships persist under alternative assumptions. Differences in inflation and human capital highlight that specific effects depend on performance thresholds or whether variation is within or across countries.

Table 6. Random-Effects Regression with Driscoll-Kraay Standard-Errors

Variable	Coef.	Std. err.	t	P> t	95% CI	
					Lower	Upper
Environmental Tax	0.317 ^a	0.043	7.340	0.000	0.225	0.409
Headline Inflation	-0.007	0.008	-0.900	0.380	-0.024	0.010
Interest Rate	-0.005	0.006	-0.940	0.363	-0.018	0.007
Physical Capital	0.724 ^a	0.045	16.050	0.000	0.628	0.820
Human Capital	0.105 ^b	0.044	2.380	0.031	0.011	0.199
GHG Emissions	-0.030 ^a	0.004	-7.660	0.000	-0.038	-0.022
Exchange Rate	-0.047 ^a	0.013	-3.610	0.003	-0.074	-0.019
Intercept	8.077 ^a	1.138	7.100	0.000	5.651	10.502
Adj. R ²	0.979					

Note: (1) ^a and ^b denote statistical significance at 1% and 5% respectively. (2) Coef. Represents the coefficient estimate. (3) Std.err refers to standard error. (4) 95% CI Lower and 95% CI Upper are the lower and upper bounds of the 95% confidence intervals, respectively. (5) t and P>|t| represent the t-statistic and the associated p-value respectively.

Table 7. Fixed-Effects Regression with Driscoll-Kraay Standard-Errors

Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	95% CI	
					Lower	Upper
Environmental Tax	0.224 ^a	0.035	6.480	0.000	0.151	0.298
Headline Inflation	-0.030 ^a	0.006	-4.710	0.000	-0.044	-0.017
Interest Rate	0.004	0.008	0.490	0.632	-0.013	0.021
Physical Capital	0.976 ^a	0.009	110.780	0.000	0.957	0.994
Human Capital	0.050	0.047	1.070	0.302	-0.050	0.149
GHG Emissions	-0.016 ^a	0.003	-4.680	0.000	-0.023	-0.009
Exchange Rate	-0.040 ^a	0.005	-8.170	0.000	-0.050	-0.029
Intercept	1.967 ^a	0.147	13.340	0.000	1.653	2.281
Adj. R ²	0.984					

Note: (1) ^a denotes statistical significance at 1% and 5% respectively. (2) Coef. Represents the coefficient estimate. (3) Std.err refers to standard error. (4) 95% CI Lower and 95% CI Upper are the lower and upper bounds of the 95% confidence intervals, respectively. (5) t and P>|t| represent the t-statistic and the associated p-value respectively.

Figure 2. *Environmental Tax → Green GDP: Distributional vs Mean Effects*

4.6 Discussion of Findings

The theoretical underpinning of environmental taxation is the Pigouvian theory, which asserts that taxes can address market failures by ensuring that the private cost of production reflects the social cost of pollution (Pigou, 2017). We find robust evidence to support this theory, as environmental taxation consistently has a positive and statistically significant impact on Green GDP across all models and methodologies. This provides empirical support for the theoretical argument that environmental taxation encourages sustainable growth in the EU by aligning private incentives with social costs. Notably, the effects are particularly pronounced at the lower quantiles of Green GDP. This finding aligns well with Pigou's reasoning, as countries that are relatively further behind in their green transition would stand to benefit more from corrective measures that change the production and consumption profiles (Olasehinde-Williams & Saint Akadiri, 2025).

We build on the Pigouvian argument and the double dividend hypothesis (Goulder, 1995), which argues that environmental taxes have a second unintended dividend of enhancing efficiency through the recycling of tax revenues, as both work under the premise of reducing environmental damage. Our results support the first dividend as environmental taxes reduce emissions and foster green growth. However, it is also clear that the declining marginal returns in greener economies correspond to the

discussion on the second unintended dividend, as, once all tax distortions or under-investments in public infrastructures are removed, it becomes more difficult to depart from the optimal configuration of pollution taxes and experience further efficiency improvements (Bovenberg & de Mooij, 1994). This suggests that for these advanced EU economies, while environmental taxation is necessary, additional elements, such as investment and revenue recycling mechanisms, are essential to sustain the green transition.

In parallel to the literature on the EKC hypothesis, we also empirically document these MEG mechanisms within the framework of the EKC. Empirical results for physical capital investment, whether measured in levels or growth rates, confirm the EKC hypothesis through its relationship with GHG emissions. Indeed, GHG emissions drag down green GDP, while only physical capital investment enables the economy to move beyond an inverted U-shape curve. Moreover, there is limited theory or empirical evidence on the channels through which exchange rate depreciation is expected to impact the EKC. In this regard, the understanding of MEG coordination within the framework of the EKC hypothesis would shed light on the impact of exchange rate depreciation. Depreciation in the exchange rate increases the costs of importing clean technologies from abroad and delays the EKC turning point between the pollution and the affluence curves (Balcilar et al., 2025).

Finally, we also empirically confirm recent theoretical developments that highlight heterogeneity in policy impact (Chu et al., 2024) using quantile-based evidence. For example, environmental tax-induced growth increases are more pronounced in nations with relatively weaker green performance. In contrast, human capital-driven green-growth synergies accrue only to more advanced economies. These empirical results suggest that there are no one-size-fits-all EU policy prescriptions, with structural and institutional heterogeneity playing a crucial role in defining country-specific growth–emission trade-offs. The asymmetric impact of inflation provides further support in this direction, with its overall adverse macroeconomic effect being driven by EU member states with weaker fundamentals.

THE EMPIRICAL FRAMEWORK COMPLEMENTS THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK, AS EVIDENCED BY THE CONFIRMATION OF PIGOUVIAN EFFICIENCY, THE FIRST CHANNEL OF THE DOUBLE DIVIDEND, AND THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMISSIONS AND CAPITAL WITHIN THE EKC FRAMEWORK, AS WELL AS HETEROGENEOUS THEORIES ON POLICY EFFECTIVENESS. THIS COHERENT PERSPECTIVE DEMONSTRATES THAT ENVIRONMENTAL TAXATION IS NOT ONLY A CORRECTIVE TOOL BUT ALSO A STRATEGIC LEVER THAT DEMONSTRATES EFFECTIVENESS BASED ON A COUNTRY'S LEVEL OF DEVELOPMENT, MACROECONOMIC STABILITY, AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This paper investigates the impact of environmental taxation on green economic growth across the EU-27, controlling for exchange rates, greenhouse gas emissions, gross capital formation, inflation, and human capital. The empirical evidence reveals that environmental taxes significantly stimulate Green GDP, particularly among economies situated at the lower end of the green growth distribution, where the marginal benefits of eco-taxation are most substantial. This underscores the unequal yet complementary role of environmental taxation across heterogeneous EU economies. In contrast, the persistent adverse effects of exchange rate depreciation and greenhouse gas emissions on Green GDP

signal structural vulnerabilities that may constrain the transition toward sustainable growth. Gross capital formation emerges as the second most influential driver, affirming the importance of physical capital accumulation—especially in green infrastructure and technology—in reinforcing long-term growth resilience. Meanwhile, inflation tends to dampen the returns on green investments, whereas human capital has positive effects, particularly in advanced economies where environmental innovation and skills adaptation are more developed.

This study advances the empirical debate by adopting a distribution-sensitive (quantile-based) framework, revealing heterogeneous effects that are obscured in traditional mean-based models. The findings point toward a multi-layered policy strategy: environmental taxation should be complemented by macroeconomic stabilisation measures, innovation-driven subsidies, and long-term investments in both human and physical capital. Such an integrated strategy is crucial to ensure that eco-taxation not only curbs emissions but also sustains competitiveness, fosters technological progress, and delivers inclusive green growth across the European Union.

5.2 Policy Insights

The findings yield several policy implications for EU economies. First, environmental taxation should remain a central component of sustainability strategies, but its design must reflect the heterogeneous growth–emission dynamics observed across the Green GDP distribution. While the study does not explicitly segment countries into groups, the quantile-based results suggest that economies at the lower end of the Green GDP distribution—typically those with higher environmental inefficiencies—stand to gain the most from broadening the environmental tax base and earmarking revenues for renewable energy, clean transportation, and circular economy initiatives. Conversely, countries positioned at the higher end of the distribution, where marginal efficiency gains are minor, should prioritise innovation-driven incentives, including targeted subsidies and demand-pull measures for advanced green technologies, to prevent policy stagnation and maintain competitiveness.

Second, the adverse effect of exchange rate depreciation underscores the need to integrate green growth strategies with macroeconomic stability frameworks. Policymakers should reinforce currency stabilisation mechanisms, reduce dependency on imported clean technologies, and foster domestic production of renewable energy components. These measures can mitigate vulnerability to external shocks and ensure that exchange rate fluctuations do not derail green investment plans.

Third, environmental taxation must transcend revenue mobilisation to deliver measurable emission reductions. Achieving this requires a shift toward tax designs that strengthen the credibility of carbon pricing, phase out fossil fuel subsidies, and expand incentives for the low-carbon sector. Such structural alignment will help internalise environmental costs and sustain progress toward the EU's climate neutrality objectives.

Fourth, the strong positive elasticity of Green GDP with respect to physical capital accumulation indicates that expanding green infrastructure investment—especially in renewable energy, transport, and green industrial technologies—can substantially enhance growth resilience. These investments also serve as buffers against climate and energy shocks, strengthening the adaptive capacity of EU economies.

Finally, while the direct quantile effects of inflation and human capital are more nuanced, the policy lessons remain evident. Maintaining credible monetary policies is vital to preventing inflationary

pressures from eroding sustainable investment. Simultaneously, developing human capital aligned with the needs of the green transition, through education, technical training, and digital skill development, will ensure that the labour force can effectively drive and sustain the transition to low-carbon economies.

In conclusion, the study highlights that environmental taxation, when complemented by coherent structural and macroeconomic policies, can yield both ecological and economic benefits. A twin-track strategy—combining eco-taxation with supportive fiscal, innovation, and human capital measures—offers the most viable path for EU member states to balance growth, equity, and sustainability in the pursuit of climate neutrality.

5.3 Limitations and Future Research Directions

While the results offer robust and policy-relevant insights, several limitations warrant acknowledgement. First, the analysis is confined to 21 EU countries due to data gaps, which may limit the generalizability of findings across the full EU-27 or to non-EU economies. Second, the study period (2005–2022) reflects the most recent span of consistent environmental tax data. However, it excludes the post-2022 policy environment shaped by evolving EU Green Deal initiatives and the energy price shocks that followed. Third, however, Green GDP provides a comprehensive indicator of environmentally adjusted growth; it may not fully capture other dimensions of ecological sustainability, such as ecosystem services, resource circularity, or well-being metrics. Future research could be expanded by incorporating non-EU comparative panels, integrating post-2022 datasets to account for recent structural and policy shifts, or testing alternative composite measures of green economic progress to validate the robustness of the results further.

REFERENCES

- Aghion, P., Dechezleprêtre, A., Hemous, D., Martin, R., & Van Reenen, J. (2016). Carbon taxes, path dependency, and directed technical change: Evidence from the auto industry. *Journal of Political Economy*, 124(1), 1-51.
- Alvarez, M. (2019). Distributional effects of environmental taxation: an approximation with a meta-regression analysis. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 62, 382–401.
- Ahmed, F., Kousar, S., Pervaiz, A., Trinidad-Segovia, J. E., del Pilar Casado-Belmonte, M., & Ahmed, W. (2022). The Role of Green Innovation, Trade, and Energy in Promoting Green Economic Growth: A Case Study of South Asian Nations. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(5), 6871-6885.
- Andersson, J. J. (2019). Carbon Taxes and CO2 Emissions: Sweden as a Case Study. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 11(4), 1-30.
- Apergis, N., & Ozturk, I. (2015). Testing the Environmental Kuznets Curve Hypothesis in Asian Countries. *Ecological indicators*, 52, 16-22.
- Andersen, M. S. (2019). The Politics of Carbon Taxation: How Varieties of Policy Style Matter. *Environmental Politics*.
- Audi, M., Poulin, M., Ahmad, K., & Ali, A. (2025). Modelling disaggregate globalisation to carbon emissions in BRICS: A panel quantile regression analysis. *Sustainability*, 17(6), 2638.
- Bekun, F. V., Gyamfi, B. A., Onifade, S. T., & Agboola, M. O. (2021). Beyond the environmental Kuznets Curve in E7 economies: accounting for the combined impacts of institutional quality

- and renewables. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 314, 127924.
- Balcilar, M., Özkan, O., Usman, O., Saint Akadiri, S., & Zambrano-Monserrate, M. A. (2025). A global shift: How modern technologies are powering the energy transition in the face of climate change. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 384, 125610.
- Bovenberg, A. L., & Goulder, L. H. (1996). Optimal environmental taxation in the presence of other taxes: general-equilibrium analyses. *The American Economic Review*, 86(4), 985-1000.
- Bosquet, B. (2000). Environmental tax reform: does it work? A survey of the empirical evidence. *Ecological economics*, 34(1), 19–32.
- Byaro, M., Rwezaula, A., & Ngowi, N. (2023). Does internet use and adoption matter for better health outcomes in sub-Saharan African countries? New evidence from panel quantile regression. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 191, 122445.
- Bovenberg, A. L., & De Mooij, R. A. (1994). Environmental levies and distortionary taxation. *The American Economic Review*, 84(4), 1085-1089.
- Bento, A. M. (2013). Equity impacts of environmental policy. *Annu. Rev. Resour. Econ.*, 5(1), 181–196.
- Chudik, A., Mohaddes, K., Pesaran, M. H., & Raissi, M. (2016). Long-run effects in large heterogeneous panel data models with cross-sectionally correlated errors. In *Essays in Honour of Man Ullah* (pp. 85–135). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Canay, I. A. (2011). A simple approach to quantile regression for panel data. *The Econometrics Journal*, 14(3), 368-386.
- Chu, L. K., Dung, H. P., & Thanh, T. T. (2024). A step towards energy efficiency in G7 countries: analysing the role of economic complexity and shadow economy on energy intensity. *Energy Efficiency*, 17(8), 97.
- Chu, L. K., Ghosh, S., Doğan, B., Nguyen, N. H., & Shahbaz, M. (2023). Energy Security as a New Determinant of Renewable Energy: The Role of Economic Complexity in Top Energy Users. *Energy*, 263, 125799.
- Costa-Campi, M. T., del Rio, P., & Trujillo-Baute, E. (2017). Trade-offs in energy and environmental policy. *Energy Policy*, 104, 415-418.
- Cho, J. S., Kim, T. H., & Shin, Y. (2015). Quantile cointegration in the autoregressive distributed-lag modelling framework. *Journal of Econometrics*, 188(1), 281–300.
- Dasgupta, S., Laplante, B., Wang, H., & Wheeler, D. (2002). Confronting the environmental Kuznets curve. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 16(1), 147–168.
- Demiral, M., & Akça, E. E. (2022). Economic complexity–carbonisation nexus in the European Union: A heterogeneous panel data analysis. *Energy Sources, Part B: Economics, Planning, and Policy*, 17(1), 2046210.
- European Commission. (2021). *Green Taxation – in support of a more sustainable future*. European Commission. Retrieved [18-2025], from Green Taxation – in support of a more sustainable future
- European Environment Agency. (2012, June 12). *Environmental tax reform: Increasing individual income, promoting innovation, and reducing pollution*. European Environment Agency
- Frodyma, K., Papież, M., & Śmiech, S. (2022). Revisiting the environmental Kuznets curve in the

- European Union countries. *Energy*, 241, 122899.
- Goulder, L. H. (1995). Environmental taxation and the double dividend: a reader's guide. *International tax and public finance*, 2(2), 157–183.
- Grossman, G. M., & Krueger, A. B. (1995). Economic growth and the environment. *The quarterly journal of economics*, 110(2), 353–377.
- Hao, L. N., Umar, M., Khan, Z., & Ali, W. (2021). Green growth and low carbon emissions in G7 countries: How critical is the network of environmental taxes, renewable energy, and human capital? *Science of the Total Environment*, 752, 141853.
- Hawitibo, A. L., & Tenaw, D. (2022). The disaggregated environmental effects of growth and distributional heterogeneity: Evidence from emerging market economies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 369, 133293.
- Im, K. S., Pesaran, M. H., & Shin, Y. (2003). Testing for unit roots in heterogeneous panels. *Journal of Econometrics*, 115(1), 53-74.
- Jordan, S., & Philips, A. Q. (2018). Cointegration testing and dynamic simulations of autoregressive distributed lag models. *The Stata Journal*, 18(4), 902–923.
- Koenker, R., & Bassett Jr, G. (1978). Regression quantiles. *Econometrica: journal of the Econometric Society*, 33–50.
- Köppl, A., & Schratzenstaller, M. (2023). Carbon taxation: A review of the empirical literature. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 37(4), 1353-1388.
- Klenert, D., Mattauch, L., Combet, E., Edenhofer, O., Hepburn, C., Rafaty, R., & Stern, N. (2018). Making carbon pricing work for citizens. *Nature Climate Change*, 8(8), 669–677.
- Khan, H., Dong, Y., Nuță, F. M., & Khan, I. (2023). Eco-innovations, green growth, and environmental taxes in EU countries: A panel quantile regression approach. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(49), 108005–108022.
- Liu, C., Ni, C., Sharma, P., Jain, V., Chawla, C., Shabbir, M. S., & Tabash, M. I. (2022). Does green environmental innovation really matter for a carbon-free economy? Nexus among green technological innovation, green international trade, and green power generation. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(45), 67504–67512.
- Li, P., Lin, Z., Du, H., Feng, T., & Zuo, J. (2021). Do environmental taxes reduce air pollution? Evidence from fossil-fuel power plants in China. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 295, 113112.
- Metcalf, G. E., & Stock, J. H. (2020). Measuring the macroeconomic impact of carbon taxes. In *AEA Papers and Proceedings* (Vol. 110, pp. 101–106). 2014 Broadway, Suite 305, Nashville, TN 37203: American Economic Association.
- Ma, X., & Zhang, J. (2016). Robust model-free feature screening via quantile correlation. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 143, 472–480.
- Morley, B. (2012). Empirical evidence on the effectiveness of environmental taxes. *Applied Economics Letters*, 19(18), 1817-1820.
- Maddala, G. S., & Wu, S. (1999). A comparative study of unit root tests with panel data and a new simple test. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 61(S1), 631–652.
- Mazzucato, M., & Perez, C. (2023). Redirecting growth: inclusive, sustainable and innovation-led.

- In *A Modern Guide to Uneven Economic Development* (pp. 71-106). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Nguyen, T. P., & Duong, T. T. T. (2025). Asymmetric Effects of Fiscal Policy and Foreign Direct Investment Inflows on CO₂ Emissions—An Application of Nonlinear ARDL. *Sustainability*, 17(6), 2503.
- Opoku, E. E. O., & Aluko, O. A. (2021). Heterogeneous effects of industrialisation on the environment: Evidence from panel quantile regression. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 59, 174–184.
- Olaschinde-Williams, G., & Folorunsho, A. (2025). Environmental Policy, Green Trade, and Sustainable Development in Europe: A New Perspective on the Porter Hypothesis. *Energy & Environment*, 36(3), 1443–1461.
- Olaschinde-Williams, G., & Köksal, C. (2025). Geoeconomic Fragmentation: What Is at Stake for the Energy Transition in the Global North? Empirical evidence from panel-quantile-type estimation methods. *Innovation and Green Development*, 4(2), 100227.
- Olaschinde-Williams, G., Omotosho, R., & Bekun, F. V. (2024). Interest rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria: New insight from the quantile autoregressive distributed lag (QARDL) model. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1–24.
- Olaschinde-Williams, G., Saint Akadiri, S., & Sambou, M. (2025). A Quantile Panel-Type Analysis of the Relationship Between Carbon Price and Energy Inflation in the EU-27. *Energy RESEARCH LETTERS*, 6(Early View).
- Olaschinde-Williams, G., & Saint Akadiri, S. (2025). European-transition climate risk pricing in international clean energy markets: Evidence from quantile dependence and directional predictability. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 392, 126936.
- OECD. (2022). *Taxing Energy Use 2019: Using Taxes for Climate Action*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/058ca239-en>
- Pesaran, M. H. (2007). A simple panel unit root test in the presence of cross-section dependence. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 22(2), 265-312.
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of applied econometrics*, 16(3), 289-326.
- Preuss, M., Reuter, W. H., & Schmidt, C. M. (2021). Distributional effects of carbon pricing in Germany. *Finanzarchiv*, 77(3), 287–316.
- Porter, M. (1996). America's green strategy. *Business and the Environment: A Reader*, 33, 1072.
- Pigou, A. (2017). *The economics of welfare*. Routledge.
- Powell, D. (2022). Quantile regression with non-additive fixed effects. *Empirical Economics*, 63(5), 2675–2691.
- Sun, Y., Belgacem, S. B., Khatoon, G., & Nazir, F. (2025). The Impact of Environmental Taxation, Green Innovation, Economic Growth, and Renewable Energy on Green Total Factor Productivity. *Gondwana Research*, 145, 218-227.
- Stern, N. (2007). *The economics of climate change: the Stern review*. Cambridge University Press.
- Stern, D. I. (2004). The Rise and Fall of the Environmental Kuznets Curve. *World development*, 32(8), 1419–1439.
- Savranlar, B., Ertas, S. A., & Aslan, A. (2024). The Role of Environmental Tax on Environmental

- Quality in EU Countries: Evidence from a Panel Vector Autoregression Approach. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 31(24), 35769-35778.
- Shahbaz, M., Lahiani, A., Abosedra, S., & Hammoudeh, S. (2018). The role of globalisation in energy consumption: A quantile cointegrating regression approach. *Energy Economics*, 71, 161–170.
- Stjepanovic, S., Tomic, D., & Skare, M. (2022). A new database on Green GDP, 1970-2019: a framework for assessing the green economy. *Oeconomia Copernicana*, 13(4), 949-975.
- Vona, F. (2021). Managing the distributional effects of environmental and climate policies: The narrow path for a triple dividend. *OECD Environment Working Papers*, (188), 0_1-61.
- Ville, K. (2023). *Labour Productivity and Development of Carbon Competitiveness: Industry-Level Evidence from Europe* (No. 139). ETLA Report.
- Wu, H., Hao, Y., & Ren, S. (2020). How do environmental regulations and environmental decentralisation affect green total factor energy efficiency? Evidence from China. *Energy Economics*, 91, 104880.
- Wolde-Rufael, Y., & Mulat-Weldemeskel, E. (2023). Effectiveness of Environmental Taxes and Stringent Environmental Policies on CO2 Emissions: The European Experience. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 25(6), 5211-5239.
- Xepapadeas, A., & de Zeeuw, A. (1999). Environmental policy and competitiveness: The Porter hypothesis and the composition of capital. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 37(2), 165-182.